

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Allocation of low-threshold special educational support in lower secondary education: The role of individual and class-level characteristics

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Abstract

It is vital that students with learning or behavioural difficulties receive special educational (SE) support from professionals. However, allocation criteria are often unclear. This issue is particularly important in lower secondary schools, where ability tracking is common and external differentiation strategies accommodate achievement differences. This cross-sectional study examines associations between low-threshold SE support and individual characteristics, class composition and school type (mixed-ability versus low-ability classes) among 941 students (aged 11–18) from 74 classrooms in German-speaking Switzerland. Logistic multilevel regression analyses revealed that SE support is more often allocated to students with low mathematics achievement, low socioeconomic status (SES), and boys, while migration background and disruptive behaviour are not significant predictors. At the classroom level, lower mean mathematics achievement is associated with a higher likelihood of SE support, although this pattern is partly explained by school type. Importantly, gender and SES remain associated with SE support even when individual mathematics achievement is considered. These findings highlight social disparities in support allocation. Merely identifying students as requiring SE support may lead to unintended consequences, such as lower expectations or stigmatization. Further research is needed to examine how structural and institutional factors determine low-threshold SE support allocation and shape students' educational trajectories.

KEYWORDS

class composition, gender, mathematics achievement, secondary school, socio-economic status, special educational support

Key Points

- Students with low mathematics achievement, those with low socioeconomic status, and boys are more likely to receive low-threshold special educational support at the lower secondary level, but there is no significant association with migration background or disruptive behaviour.
- A lower mean mathematics achievement in a classroom increases the likelihood of receiving low-threshold support. This is partly related to school type at the secondary level (mixed-ability versus low-ability classes).

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- Even when individual achievement is considered, gender and socioeconomic status remain linked to low-threshold support, indicating social inequalities affecting allocation.
- While special educational support can benefit students, its allocation may also reinforce social disparities and carry the risk of stigmatization, underlining the need for research on structural and institutional influences.

INTRODUCTION

Providing adequate support for students with special educational needs, such as learning and behavioural difficulties, is a key element of fair access to education. In many educational systems, the implementation of inclusive education, where students with diverse learning needs and achievement levels are taught together in one classroom, is expanding at all school levels (Kuhl et al., 2022; Williamson et al., 2020). As a result, classrooms have become increasingly heterogeneous, making differentiated instruction critical (Pozas et al., 2021). Differentiated instruction involves tailoring support to meet the needs of all of the students in a classroom. This can involve, for example, flexible time arrangements that allow learners to work at different paces, ability grouping based on learner performance or interests, tutoring systems, and Open Education Practice (Pozas et al., 2021, p. 2). However, research conducted in primary schools shows that differentiated instruction alone cannot always meet students' learning and behavioural needs (Deunk et al., 2018). Therefore, in inclusive settings there is often additional special educational (SE) support delivered by special education teachers. The teachers support the general education teacher in the classroom, engage in co-teaching and give assistance to small groups or individuals. The purpose of SE support is to ensure that students with learning or behavioural difficulties receive targeted assistance while continuing to be taught in a general classroom. Research has demonstrated that collaboration between general and special education teachers has a positive effect on students' perceived learning support (Luger et al., 2024). However, the allocation of support also carries potential risks. Being identified as needing special support may lead to labeling effects and stigmatization, affect teacher expectations and influence students' academic self-concepts, with possible long-term consequences for educational trajectories and transitions into the labour market (Algraigray & Doyle, 2017; Norwich, 2014; Sahli Lozano et al., 2023). Moreover, there is evidence that receiving SE support does not necessarily improve academic outcomes and can sometimes even have a negative effect on achievement by narrowing the curriculum or reducing academic expectations (Kvande et al., 2019). Therefore, understanding which students are allocated to SE support and how this allocation is affected by individual and contextual characteristics is crucial for assessing

the equity and effectiveness of support systems. This is particularly important because research has revealed considerable variation in how special educational needs are identified. The diagnostic criteria and the assignment of support measures (Gasterstädt et al., 2021; Luder, 2021; Norwich, 2014; Sahli Lozano et al., 2023), and the classification and implementation of SE support varies between countries and regions (Grünke & Cavendish, 2016; Sahli Lozano et al., 2021). Studies have also shown that students from families with a low socioeconomic status (SES),ⁱ those with a migration background, and boys are more likely to be allocated to SE support (Cooc & Kiru, 2018; Kölm et al., 2020; Kvande et al., 2018; Sahli Lozano et al., 2023). These findings call for greater attention to potential inequalities in the allocation of SE support.

In the Swiss context the term inclusive education refers to an instructional setting where students with and without special educational needs are taught together (Luder, 2021). All students attend the same class and spend most of their instructional time in a shared classroom environment. Support is provided by special education teachers,ⁱⁱ who either co-teach with the general education teacher or deliver targeted interventions to address the needs of individual students or small groups. Co-teaching, defined as the joint planning and delivery of instruction by general and special education teachers, can take various forms, including one teach/one assist, parallel teaching and teaming.

The support provided by special education teachers is part of a multi-level special education support system (Bildungsdirektion Kanton Zürich (BIZH), 2018) comprised of low-threshold and intensive measures (EDK, 2023). These formal measures are distinct from general classroom-based instructional support and are subject to specific allocation procedures. Students are only assigned to intensive measures if low-threshold measures have been shown to be insufficient. Intensive support is intended for students with severe and enduring impairments such as intellectual disabilities, motor disabilities, or severe behavioural troubles. Funding follows an input model (Meijer, 1999), meaning that resources are allocated for a specific student's needs; they require a formal diagnosis (Kronenberg, 2021). The diagnosis is based on a standardized assessment conducted by a specialist (e.g. school psychologist). In contrast, low-threshold support for students experiencing learning or behavioural difficulties does not require a formal diagnosis (BIZH, 2022; Luder, 2021). Low-threshold support

is funded using a throughput model based on population indicators (e.g., number of pupils enrolled in a school, local social indices; Meijer, 1999). Throughput models are based on aggregate indicators at the school or system level and not on individual diagnoses. In this model, schools receive a lump sum—a fixed overall budget for SE support—and are able to decide how to distribute them. Allocation decisions for low-threshold support are usually made by school principals, in consultation with parents, using teacher assessments. There are no set diagnostic criteria or standardized procedures and the target group for low-threshold measures is loosely defined (Kronenberg, 2021; Sahli Lozano et al., 2023). The measures used to deliver low-threshold support are not governed by any binding guidelines or standardized allocation procedures. Schools define their own processes, which are usually specified in the school's policy documents. As a result, it is unclear whether the allocation of low-threshold support measures is a reflection of actual student needs or the result of social and contextual factors.

The question of how SE support is allocated is particularly important in lower secondary school because students are generally tracked on the basis of academic ability at this level (Konferenz der kantonalen Erziehungsdirektorinnen und -direktoren (EDK), 2024; Kultusminister Konferenz der Länder in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland (KMK), 2011). How tracking is organized varies between cantons and even between schools within cantons. Some schools have separate classes based on student ability levels (e.g., low-ability versus high-ability classes), while others have mixed-ability classes. Placement into ability levels is generally based on an overall assessment of the student by teachers, including special education teachers. Parents and students are also involved, but the degree of their involvement varies from canton to canton. Although tracking is primarily intended to reflect differences in academic achievement, research shows that student characteristics such as SES, migration background and gender also play a role (Dumont et al., 2014; Felouzis & Charmillot, 2023). Since school assignment in Switzerland is usually based on place of residence, class composition tends to mirror the sociodemographic composition of the local population. Notwithstanding the influence of locality, students from low-SES families, those with a migration background, and boys are disproportionately represented in low-ability classes (Dumont et al., 2014; Felouzis & Charmillot, 2023). Students who are defined as having special educational needs are also more frequently assigned to these low-ability classes (Müller & Hofmann, 2016; Ruijs, 2017). Ability tracking is intended to address differences in achievement. However, it is unclear whether students with learning and behavioural difficulties receive additional SE support in addition to this placement, or whether being assigned to a lower track is considered sufficient to meet their needs.

Other contextual factors are also likely to play a role. One such factor is class composition. There is evidence that class composition may influence the likelihood of a student receiving SE support. Studies at the primary level indicate that the probability of receiving SE support for students with learning difficulties increases in classes with higher achievement levels (Hibel et al., 2010; Kölm et al., 2020; Koßmann et al., 2024).

Against this background, the present study examines the allocation of low-threshold SE support in lower secondary schools in German-speaking Switzerland.

SE SUPPORT IN RELATION TO INDIVIDUAL AND CLASS-LEVEL CHARACTERISTICS

The impact of individual characteristics

Several studies have demonstrated that certain individual characteristics affect whether a student is allocated special education measures. Low academic achievement is one of the most reliable predictors for receiving SE support (Hibel et al., 2010; Kölm et al., 2020; Koßmann et al., 2024). Within that category, when different domains of achievement are considered, mathematics achievement emerges as a particularly strong predictor: it has been found that individual differences in mathematics are more strongly related to the identification of special educational needs and receiving SE support than reading achievement (Kölm et al., 2020; Koßmann et al., 2024).

However, research also suggests that academic achievement alone does not fully explain the allocation of SE support. Students from socially less privileged families, students with a migration background and boys are consistently overrepresented in special education settings (Cooc & Kiru, 2018). These same characteristics also appear to play a significant role in the allocation of SE support in inclusive education. Boys are more frequently allocated to SE support than girls (Daniel & Wang, 2023; Hibel et al., 2010; Kvande et al., 2018). Students from families with a low SES and those with a migration background are also more likely to receive support (Kölm et al., 2020; Kvande et al., 2018; Sahli Lozano et al., 2023). The effect of migration background may be reduced when SES and migration background are considered simultaneously (Kölm et al., 2020). In addition to these demographic factors, behavioural difficulty is often associated with an increased likelihood of receiving SE support (Schwab et al., 2019).

There are several mechanisms that could explain these patterns. The higher proportion of boys with SE support, compared to girls, may in part be an artefact of the allocation process. In many countries, SE support allocation requires a formal diagnosis. Diagnoses such as Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)

or Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) are more frequent among boys than among girls (Fish, 2019). Boys also more frequently display behaviours that conflict with instructional situations that require sustained attention, quiet seatwork and language-based participation, which can make difficulties more visible and support needs more salient (Godwin et al., 2016).

The social background of students can have an influence on the allocation of SE support. Boudon's (1974) concept of primary and secondary effects provides a useful framework for explaining the development of educational inequalities based on social class (Maaz et al., 2009; Sahli Lozano et al., 2023). Social background influences learning conditions and resources. Students from socially less privileged families often have more limited access to learning-related resources and support such as books, tutoring or structured learning routines. This can affect academic achievement (primary effect). Social background can also have a secondary effect on educational decisions such as school placement or access to support measures—family social background influences levels of educational aspiration, access to information and the ability to actively pursue support measures. For example, students from socially less privileged families may have both lower academic achievement and less ambitious educational aspirations (Maaz et al., 2009). Because decisions about the allocation of SE support usually involve parents, parental attitudes, aspirations and perceptions of what support measures signal may directly affect these decisions. These secondary effects may also reflect the reality that families from different social backgrounds vary in their willingness or ability to agree to and actively pursue support measures.

Similarly, the relevance of student migration background can be explained by a combination of language-related, cultural and family background mechanisms. Limited proficiency in the language of instruction can affect students' academic achievement (Volodina et al., 2021). The higher likelihood of students with a migration background receiving SE support can be attributed to parents' limited familiarity with the local education system, possible reduced parental support and constraints on parental involvement in decision-making processes, which may affect both educational trajectories and access to support measures (Cooc & Kiru, 2018; Dumont et al., 2014).

These mechanisms are closely intertwined. Once assigned to SE support, students have a higher probability of remaining in an SE support setting with low expectations in the future and this can contribute to the persistence of differences (Kvande et al., 2018). Students from socially less privileged backgrounds, those with a migration background and boys might also be more affected because their behaviour may deviate from dominant classroom norms (Cooc & Kiru, 2018; Daniel & Wang, 2023; Neuenschwander &

Garrote, 2024). Therefore, it is also important to consider information on student behaviour when investigating this issue.

Having behavioural difficulties is one of the recognized criteria for allocating SE support (Norwich, 2014). It is also the case that behavioural difficulties frequently co-occur with learning difficulties (Börnert-Ringleb et al., 2019), increasing the need for targeted support. Students with behavioural difficulties need to receive adequate support to address both behavioural and learning-related needs (Becherer et al., 2021; Börnert-Ringleb et al., 2019). However, the research findings are not always consistent. For example, Koßmann et al. (2024) found no association between challenging behaviour and the allocation of SE support.

How student characteristics are perceived and evaluated also play a role in support allocation. Teacher judgements and referral decisions are not only shaped by performance indicators but also by social and cultural factors, including implicit biases, stereotypes and peer-comparison processes (Childs & Wooten, 2022; Hibel et al., 2010). These processes can result in teachers attributing lower ability or the need for more support to certain groups of students, such as those from less privileged families, those with migration backgrounds or boys, thus increasing the likelihood of referral to SE support (Glock et al., 2022; Petsko et al., 2022; Pit-ten Cate & Glock, 2018).

The relevance of class composition and school type in secondary education

Class composition can also influence the allocation of SE support (Hibel et al., 2010; Kölm et al., 2020; Koßmann et al., 2024). When the proportion of students with a migration background and the mean SES in a class are considered together, the probability of receiving SE support increases in classes with higher achievement levels (Hibel et al., 2010; Kölm et al., 2020; Koßmann et al., 2024). Previous research explains this effect with the Frog-Pond Theory (Davis, 1966; Farkas et al., 1990). This theory postulates that teachers assess students relative to their classmates, meaning that in heterogeneous classes, students with achievement levels significantly higher or lower than the average may attract more attention, impacting the assessment of students as well as the allocation of support (Kölm et al., 2020). Since receiving SE support is closely linked to academic achievement (Kölm et al., 2020), explanations for the effect of class composition on achievement found in the literature are relevant for an analysis of SE support allocation. Dumont et al. (2013) highlight teacher expectations as a mechanism through which class composition may affect student achievement. In low-achieving classes, teachers may have lower

expectations and adopt a slower pace of teaching, exacerbating existing gaps in achievement. This aligns with the concept of the Pygmalion effect (Rosenthal & Jacobson, 1966), where teacher expectations can influence student achievement.

Because ability tracking is common at the lower secondary level, the composition of the student population is closely linked to school type, which in turn has a significant influence on learning opportunities (Baumert et al., 2006; Dumont et al., 2013). There are consistent differences between the learning environments of each track. Student characteristics associated with educational disadvantage do not affect all school types or educational tracks equally. Students with low academic achievement, from socially less privileged families, with a migration background and boys are overrepresented in classes with low academic requirements (Baumert et al., 2006; Cooc & Kiru, 2018; Felouzis & Charmillot, 2023; Kronenberg, 2021; Müller & Hofmann, 2016; Stanat et al., 2010). This leads to the assumption that such track assignments are influenced not only by prior achievement but also by social and linguistic resources, parental familiarity with the school system and teacher expectations. As these characteristics often overlap (Becker & Birkelbach, 2017; Stanat et al., 2010), students in low-ability classes often experience a less favourable learning environment, whereas students in high-ability tracks generally benefit from more advantageous ones. Classes with high academic requirements are typically characterized by a more socioeconomically and academically advantaged student composition. Even though research examining class composition at the lower secondary level in Switzerland is limited, patterns of social and academic stratification have been documented (Felouzis & Charmillot, 2023). Creating mixed-ability classrooms by combining students from different tracks may reduce compositional effects and their impact (Felouzis & Charmillot, 2023).

To sum up, the state of research indicates that the allocation of SE support needs to be interpreted in light of systematically different learning conditions across school tracks and classroom contexts. The concentration of multiple disadvantage-related characteristics in low-ability classes may increase support requirements overall, and classroom composition and school type can have an influence on the identification of need for and allocation of SE support that is not necessarily a fair reflection of a student's actual needs. However, the extent to which SE support allocation in lower secondary school stems from individual characteristics (e.g. SES, migration background, gender, achievement and behaviour) versus the degree to which it is shaped by contextual factors such as class composition or school type remains unclear. Understanding how these factors relate to the allocation of SE support is essential for examining patterns of support allocation in secondary education. This study therefore focuses on investigating these relationships.

RESEARCH QUESTION AND HYPOTHESES

While there has been a great deal of research on identifying individual-level predictors of SE allocation, such as gender, SES and migration background, much of this work has focused on traditional forms of segregated special education, such as special schools or separate classes, rather than on SE support provided by special education teachers in inclusive educational settings. Moreover, the role of student behaviour in SE support allocation remains inconclusive (Kobmann et al., 2024). Little is known about how these individual characteristics relate to the compositional characteristics of the classroom and the school type, especially at the secondary level. Most studies that consider classroom composition focus on primary education (Hibel et al., 2010; Kölm et al., 2020; Kobmann et al., 2024).

For the Swiss context, this gap is further reinforced by the absence of systematic data on low-threshold measures, meaning that there is no systematic information on how these measures are allocated, which students receive the support, and the extent to which the allocation of this support is related to individual characteristics and/or the class-level context. Because these measures are less formalized and do not require a diagnosis, existing research provides only limited insights into how individual and class-level characteristics are associated with their allocation. Against this background, it is particularly important to investigate how low-threshold SE support is allocated in secondary education and how its distribution relates to student and class-level characteristics.

The present study aims to contribute to closing this research gap by examining associations between low-threshold SE support on both individual- and class-level characteristics in lower secondary schools in German-speaking Switzerland.

In light of the issues discussed above, this study aims to answer the following question:

Which individual and class-level characteristics predict the likelihood of a student receiving low-threshold SE support at the lower secondary level?

Based on prior empirical findings, the following hypotheses are postulated. In all hypotheses, low-threshold SE support is specified as the dependent variable, while individual and class-level characteristics are included as independent variables (predictors).

H1. Individual student characteristics.

Each of the following student characteristics—being a boy, having a low SES, a migration background, low mathematics achievement or behavioural difficulties—is associated with a higher likelihood of receiving SE support.

H2. Class composition characteristics.

A higher proportion of students with low SES, a migration background, low mathematics achievement, or behavioural difficulties in a class is associated with a lower likelihood of individual students receiving SE support.

H3. School type: Mixed-ability versus low-ability classes.

If a school has tracks with separate classes for high-, middle- and low ability students, the individual students in low-ability classes will have a lower likelihood of receiving SE support than if they were in a school with mixed-ability classes.

The three hypotheses are derived from existing research (see Section 2). Hypothesis 1 is based on previous studies showing that boys and students with a low SES, those with a migration background, those with behavioural difficulties and those with low academic achievement are more likely to receive SE support. Hypothesis 2 looks at the impact of class composition characteristics while continuing to account for individual characteristics. Research in primary schools has found that a higher mean class achievement increases the likelihood of students receiving SE support. In secondary education, where students are tracked by ability, a similar mechanism is expected: in classes with a lower mean achievement level and a higher proportion of students with risk factors, the likelihood of receiving SE support is lower. Finally, Hypothesis 3 focuses on school type. Because ability tracking is closely linked to achievement levels, it can be inferred that low-ability classes—where mean achievement is typically lower than in mixed-ability classes—are less likely to provide additional SE support. In a sense, tracking itself can be seen as a structural response to disparities in achievement, which may reduce the perceived need for further individual support measures.

Previous studies have shown that mathematics achievement has a particularly strong association with the allocation of SE support; more so than achievement in other academic domains such as reading (Kölm et al., 2020; Koßmann et al., 2024). Therefore, mathematics achievement is used as an indicator of overall academic achievement. Behavioural difficulties are operationalized using a scale of disruptive behaviour.

METHOD

Sample and procedure

This study is part of the project ‘The effect of segregated and inclusive education, teaching quality, and teacher characteristics on students in secondary school (SINUS)’, conducted over the first and second year of lower secondary school in nine German-speaking

cantons in Switzerland. Analyses are based on cross-sectional data on individual student characteristics and the allocation of SE support. In total, 83 classes were initially sampled using a convenience design. However, low-threshold SE support is not offered in all classes; classes without SE support—this applies also to high-ability and special classes—were therefore excluded from the sample. As a result, the final analytic sample comprises 74 classes from 25 schools with 941 students (ages 11–18; $M=13.2$, $SD=1.03$), of whom 425 (45.2%) were girls. Forty classes were in schools with mixed-ability tracking, where students from two to three tracks are taught together in one classroom. In these settings students with different achievement levels learn together and teachers are expected to provide differentiated instruction in the classroom. Thirty-four classes were entirely composed of students of low-ability. Recruitment was conducted through online newsletters from cantonal authorities and teacher training institutions. Participation was voluntary and written informed consent was obtained from both students and parents after they were provided with detailed information. A student questionnaire and mathematics test were administered during regular school hours by trained research assistants. Each participating class received a voucher as a token of appreciation. The participation rate was 79.0%, with an average of 75.6% students per class participating. The study was approved by the ethics committee of the Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences of the University of Zurich.

Instruments

The data were collected from teachers, students and their parents using (digital) questionnaires.

Teacher questionnaire:

- SE support: Does a student receive low-threshold support from a special education teacher (0=no, 1=yes)?
- Disruptive behaviour: Scale for ‘Disruptive Behaviour’ⁱⁱⁱ—used as an indicator of students’ broader behavioural difficulties—consisting of seven items (e.g., ‘made noise’; Eckstein et al., 2018; Cronbach’s alpha in this study=0.88).
- School type: Does the student attend a mixed-ability class (0) or a low-ability class (1)?

Parent and student questionnaire:

- Migration background: Information on the country of birth of the child and parents (OECD (The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development), 2018b; 0=child and at least one parent born in Switzerland, 1=child born abroad or both parents born abroad)
- Gender (0= male, 1= female, 2= diverse^{iv})

TABLE 1 Correlation coefficient for bivariate relations between individual-level variables in the analytical sample.

	1	2	3	4	5
1. Gender	—				
2. Migration background	0.02	—			
3. SES	-0.04	-0.20***	—		
4. Mathematics achievement	-0.20***	-0.27***	0.17***	—	
5. Disruptive behaviour	-0.02	0.08*	-0.04	-0.05	—

Note: Gender is coded as 0=male and 1=female.

* $p < 0.05$. *** $p < 0.001$.

Student questionnaire:

- Socioeconomic status (SES): PISA family wealth possessions (WEALTH)^v scale for measuring family wealth consisting of eight items (e.g., number of electronic devices, bathrooms and musical instruments; OECD, 2018b), with a reliability=0.76 in this study, as indicated by the weighted likelihood estimate (WLE; Warm, 1989)
- Mathematics test: 46 items on basic mathematical skills, such as mental arithmetic, place value system, understanding of fractions, decimals and percentages, and applied math problems; the test does not cover the full curriculum—it assesses basic mathematical competencies (development based on Holzer et al., 2017; Kuhl et al., 2022; Moser Opitz et al., 2021; Cronbach's alpha in this study=0.95). Achievement in mathematics is used as an indicator of student academic achievement.

Analysis

All analyses were conducted using R 4.4.3 (R Core Team, 2025). Chi-square tests, *t*-tests and correlations were used to examine baseline differences and associations between the study variables. To test Hypotheses 1–3 (individual- and class-level predictors of SE support), logistic multilevel regression models with random intercepts (Raudenbush & Bryk, 2002) were estimated using the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2015). This allowed the nested data structure (students within classes) to be taken into account and individual-level associations to be distinguished from class-level characteristics. Imputations for missing values were created with the *mice* package in R, using its functionality for multilevel data (van Buuren & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011). This resulted in 20 imputed datasets. In line with Hypothesis 1 (Model 1) the model included student gender, SES, migration background,^{vi} mathematics achievement and disruptive behaviour, entered simultaneously at the individual level. Class-level compositional variables were then added sequentially to examine compositional effects (Hypothesis 2), following a hierarchical approach

(Models 2.1–2.4). We first introduced the compositional variable with the strongest effect reported in previous research, the class mean achievement level, into the model. Additional compositional characteristics were then added based on their relevance for secondary education, reflecting the fact that track placement can be influenced by individual characteristics such as SES, migration background and behaviour. School type was included as an adjustment variable to capture structural differences between educational tracks at the secondary level (Hypothesis 3, Model 3).

SES for each student, using the PISA WEALTH scale (OECD, 2018a), was calculated as a WLE (Warm, 1989). Mathematics achievement was measured as a sum score, and disruptive behaviour was calculated as the mean of the seven-point scale. These metric individual-level variables were z-standardized. To analyse compositional effects, the corresponding variables were aggregated at the class level and group mean centered.

The results of the multilevel regression analyses are presented as average marginal effects in percentage points (AME_%), odds ratios (OR), confidence intervals (CI) and significance levels (*p*). The AME represents the average change in the probability of transitioning to a specific category (e.g., whether an individual receives SE support or not) in percentage points (Arel-Bundock et al., 2024). The OR indicates the odds of an event occurring relative to the baseline, comparing the odds of receiving SE support for one category versus another (Kalisch & Meier, 2021). Unlike the AME, which focuses on the direct change in probability, the OR reflects the relative likelihood of the event occurring across different levels of the predictor.

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics and relations between variables

We first report descriptive statistics and bivariate relations between the individual and class-level variables, followed by group comparisons and the multilevel regression analyses.

Tables 1 and 2 present the bivariate relations between individual- and class-level variables in the analytical sample, based on correlation coefficients.

The correlation matrix (Table 1) reveals that the migration background has a negative correlation with both SES ($r = -0.20$, $p < 0.001$) and mathematics achievement ($r = -0.27$, $p < 0.001$). This indicates that students with a migration background tend to have a lower SES and lower mathematics achievement. SES has a positive correlation with mathematics achievement ($r = 0.17$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that a higher SES is associated with higher mathematics achievement. Disruptive behaviour has a weak positive correlation with migration background ($r = 0.08$, $p = 0.015$), indicating that students with a migration background may show more disruptive behaviour.

Table 2 shows that all the class composition characteristics—proportion of students with a migration background, mean SES, mean mathematics achievement and

mean level of disruptive behaviour—significantly correlate with each other. This indicates that there is a high degree of confounding between aggregated individual characteristics within classes. All variables except for disruptive behaviour show significant correlations with school type, indicating differences in student composition across school type.

Table 3 presents descriptive statistics for students with and without SE support. Non-standardized values are reported. Group differences between students receiving SE support (Support_{yes}) and those not receiving SE support (Support_{no}) were tested for significance using the chi-square test (for frequencies) and the *t*-test (for mean values). Significant differences between groups were found for individual characteristics: Boys ($\chi^2(1) = 8.55$, $p = 0.003$) and students with a migration background ($\chi^2(1) = 9.90$, $p = 0.002$) are significantly overrepresented in the SE support group. Students receiving support show significant lower mean values for SES ($t(901) = 3.52$, $p < 0.001$,

TABLE 2 Correlation coefficients for bivariate relations between class-level variables in the analytical sample.

	1	2	3	4	5
1. Proportion with migration background	—				
2. Mean SES	-0.45***	—			
3. Mean mathematics achievement	-0.56***	0.43***	—		
4. Mean disruptive behaviour	0.26***	-0.08*	-0.06	—	
5. School type	0.41***	-0.42***	-0.63***	0.01	—

Note: School type is coded as 0=mixed-ability classes and 1=low-ability classes.

* $p < 0.05$. *** $p < 0.001$.

TABLE 3 Descriptive statistics for individual characteristics of students with and without SE support.

	Total N (%)	Support _{no} n (%)	Support _{yes} n (%)	Significance
Total number of students	941 (100)	234 (78.0)	207 (22.0)	
Gender				
Girls	425 (45.2)	350 (47.7)	75 (36.2)	**
Migration background				
Yes	438 (46.6)	321 (43.7)	117 (56.5)	**
Missing	7 (0.7)	7 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	
SES ^a				
M (SD)	-0.0 (1.3)	0.12 (1.3)	-0.3 (1.1)	***
Missing	38 (4.0)	31 (4.2)	7 (3.4)	
Mathematics achievement				
M (SD)	25.0 (11.9)	26.8 (11.3)	18.4 (11.6)	***
Missing	44 (4.7)	28 (3.8)	16 (7.7)	
Disruptive behaviour				
M (SD)	1.9 (1.1)	1.8 (1.0)	2.2 (1.3)	***
Missing	12 (1.3)	11 (1.5)	1 (0.5)	

Abbreviations: %, percentage of reference group; M, arithmetic mean; *n*, number of students; SD, standard deviation; SES, socio-economic status.

^aThe SES is given as a weighted likelihood estimate (WLE; Warm, 1989); based on PISA (OECD, 2018a; see Section 4.3).

** $p < 0.01$. *** $p < 0.001$.

$d=0.28$) and mathematics achievement ($t(895)=9.02$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.74$), while the mean value for disruptive behaviour is significantly higher ($t(901)=-5.49$, $p<0.001$, $d=-0.43$).

Table 4 shows the descriptive statistics for the class-level variables, with aggregated values categorized by school type: mixed-ability classes and low-ability classes.

There are significant differences in class composition between school types (**Table 4**). The proportion of students receiving SE support in low-ability classes is significantly higher than that in mixed-ability classes ($\chi^2(1)=5.38$, $p=0.020$). These classes also have a higher proportion of students with a migration background ($\chi^2(1)=38.38$, $p<0.001$), and lower mean values for mathematics achievement ($t(894.32)=10.96$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.73$) and for SES ($t(873.19)=4.90$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.33$) compared to mixed-ability classes. Disruptive behaviour is significantly more frequent in low-ability classes ($t(797.50)=-4.47$, $p<0.001$, $d=-0.30$); mixed-ability classes show lower levels of disruptive behaviour. There is no significant difference in gender composition between types of school ($\chi^2(1)=0.25$, $p=0.620$).

Relationship between individual characteristics and the allocation of SE support (Hypothesis 1)

Hypothesis 1 examines the association between individual characteristics—gender, SES, migration background, mathematics achievement, disruptive behaviour—and the likelihood of being allocated to SE support. SE support was specified as the dependent variable, while the

individual characteristics were independent variables (predictors). The results of the logistic regression analysis with individual-level predictors (Model 1) are presented in **Table 5**.

Model 1 reveals that students with low mathematics achievement ($AME_{\%}=-0.11$, $p<0.001$), students with low SES ($AME_{\%}=-0.03$, $p=0.037$) and boys ($AME_{\%}=-0.13$, $p<0.001$) are significantly more likely to receive SE support. Migration background ($AME_{\%}=0.00$, $p=0.898$) and disruptive behaviour ($AME_{\%}=0.00$, $p=0.953$) do not predict SE support.

Hypothesis 1, which postulated that students with low SES, a migration background, low mathematics achievement and disruptive behaviour, and who are boys, are more likely to receive SE support, can be partially confirmed: low mathematics achievement, low SES and being a boy are associated with a higher likelihood of receiving SE support, whereas migration background and disruptive behaviour are not.

Relationship between class composition and receiving SE support (Hypothesis 2)

Hypothesis 2 considers the effect class composition has on the likelihood of an individual student receiving SE support. The results of the logistic multilevel regression analyses are presented in **Table 6a,b**.

In Model 2.1, the mean mathematics achievement level of the class is added at level 2 to test effects of class composition. The results show that the individual-level predictors, which were significant in Model 1—low mathematics achievement, low SES and being a boy—remain significant when considering the mean mathematics

TABLE 4 Distribution of individual student characteristics by school type.

	Total <i>N</i> (%)	Mixed-ability classes <i>n</i> (%)	Low-ability classes <i>n</i> (%)	Significance
Total number of students	941 (100)	501 (53.2)	440 (46.8)	
SE support				
Yes	207 (22.0)	95 (10.1)	112 (11.9)	*
Gender				
Girls	425 (45.2)	222 (44.3)	203 (46.1)	
Migration background				
Yes	438 (46.9)	184 (37.2)	254 (57.7)	***
SES ^a				
M (SD)	-0.02 (1.26)	0.17 (1.23)	-0.24 (1.27)	***
Mathematics achievement				
M (SD)	25.0 (11.9)	28.9 (11.8)	20.7 (10.5)	***
Disruptive behaviour				
M (SD)	1.9 (1.1)	1.7 (0.9)	2.0 (1.2)	***

^aThe SES is given as a weighted likelihood estimate (WLE; Warm, 1989) based on PISA (OECD, 2018a; see Section 4.3).

* $p<0.05$. *** $p<0.001$.

TABLE 5 Logistic regression model: Likelihood of receiving SE support based on individual characteristics.

Predictors	Model 1		
	AME _%	OR [CI]	<i>p</i>
Individual level			
Gender	-0.13***	0.41 [0.31; 0.62]	0.000
Migration background	0.00	1.02 [0.73; 1.44]	0.898
SES	-0.03*	0.83 [0.69; 0.99]	0.037
Mathematics achievement	-0.11***	0.49 [0.40; 0.59]	0.000
Disruptive behaviour	0.00	1.00 [0.94; 1.07]	0.953

Note: $R^2_{\text{Model 1}} = 0.11$.

Abbreviations: AME, average marginal effect; CI, 95% confidence interval; OR, odds ratio; *p*, significance.

* $p < 0.05$. *** $p < 0.001$.

achievement level. The mean mathematics achievement level of the class becomes significant ($\text{AME}_{\%} = -0.06$, $p = 0.003$). This indicates that students in classes with lower mean mathematics achievement are more likely to receive SE support.

When additional class composition characteristics—SES, migration background and disruptive behaviour—are added (Models 2.2–2.4), the effect of the mean mathematics achievement remains stable ($\text{AME}_{\%} = -0.06$). The individual-level predictors remain significant even when compositional characteristics are considered: boys ($\text{AME}_{\%} = -0.12$, $p < 0.001$), students with low SES ($\text{AME}_{\%} = -0.03$, $p = 0.036$) and students with low mathematics achievement ($\text{AME}_{\%} = -0.13$, $p < 0.001$) are still more likely to receive SE support.

Hypothesis 2, postulating an association between class composition and the allocation of SE support at the individual level, must be rejected in its proposed form; only the mean mathematics achievement at the class level shows a significant effect. However, the effect is opposite to what was expected: the lower the mean mathematics achievement in a class, the higher the likelihood that individual students receive SE support. Other compositional characteristics, such as the proportion of students with a migration background or mean SES and mean disruptive behaviour show no significant effects.

Relationship between school type and receiving SE support (Hypothesis 3)

Hypothesis 3 involves considering school type in addition to compositional characteristics to analyse the likelihood of an individual student receiving SE support. The results of the logistic multilevel regression analyses are presented in Table 7.

When the school type is added as a class-level predictor (Model 3), the significance of the mean achievement

level of the class decreases slightly ($\text{AME}_{\%} = 0.06$, $p = 0.070$). However, the individual-level predictors—gender ($\text{AME}_{\%} = -0.12$, $p < 0.001$), SES ($\text{AME}_{\%} = -0.03$, $p = 0.037$) and individual mathematics achievement ($\text{AME}_{\%} = -0.13$, $p < 0.001$)—remain significant for predicting SE support.

Hypothesis 3, postulating an association between school type and the allocation of SE support at the individual level, must be rejected. When class composition characteristics are controlled for, school type is not a significant predictor, implying that students in low-ability classes are not less likely to receive SE support than students in mixed-ability ones.

DISCUSSION

Predictive individual and class-level characteristics

This study examined the allocation of low-threshold SE support at the lower secondary level, examining associations with individual- and class-level characteristics. The aim of this study was to investigate how individual characteristics are related to the allocation of SE support while also considering the contextual factors of class composition and school type. Our results largely align with previous research, most of which focused on primary schools and particularly examined the role of individual characteristics. There were, however, some differences.

Achievement drives SE support, but gender and SES disparities persist

Our findings confirm previous research showing that boys, students with low mathematics achievement and those with low SES are more likely to receive SE support (e.g., Cooc & Kiru, 2018; Kölm et al., 2020; Sahli Lozano et al., 2023). Mathematics achievement and gender emerged as the strongest predictors, followed by SES. These were effects that persisted even when class composition and school type were considered. Since the association between gender and SES remains robust when mathematics achievement is controlled for, this raises questions about the underlying mechanisms that drive these allocation processes. If academic achievement does not fully explain SE support allocation, then the question is what other factors might contribute to the disproportionate identification of some student groups. On the one hand, allocating SE support primarily based on mathematics achievement can be considered beneficial, as it ensures that students with academic difficulties receive targeted assistance. On the other hand, being assigned to SE support may also lead to lower teacher expectations and/or labeling effects, which can in turn shape students' academic achievement and their subsequent educational trajectories

TABLE 6 Logistic regression models: Likelihood of receiving SE support based on characteristics of class composition.

(a)						
Predictor	Model 2.1			Model 2.2		
	AME_%	OR [CI]	p	AME_%	OR [CI]	p
Individual level						
Gender	−0.12***	0.43 [0.38, 0.48]	0.000	−0.12***	0.43 [0.39, 0.47]	0.000
Migration background	0.03	1.22 [1.08, 1.39]	0.307	0.03	1.22 [1.11, 1.34]	0.417
SES	−0.03*	0.80 [0.75, 0.86]	0.033	−0.03*	0.80 [0.76, 0.85]	0.033
Mathematics achievement	−0.13***	0.40 [0.37, 0.44]	0.000	−0.13***	0.40 [0.37, 0.44]	0.000
Disruptive behaviour	0.00	1.00 [0.96, 1.04]	0.945	0.00	1.00 [0.96, 1.04]	0.931
Class level						
Mathematics achievement	−0.06**	0.65 [0.56, 0.75]	0.003	−0.06*	0.67 [0.60, 0.76]	0.013
SES				−0.12	0.89 [0.67, 1.17]	0.520
Migration background						
Disruptive behaviour						
(b)						
Predictor	Model 2.3			Model 2.4		
	AME_%	OR [CI]	p	AME_%	OR [CI]	p
Individual level						
Gender	−0.12***	0.43 [0.35, 0.53]	0.000	−0.12***	0.43 [0.34, 0.54]	0.000
Migration background	0.03	1.25 [1.00, 1.56]	0.336	0.03	1.25 [0.98, 1.60]	0.337
SES	−0.03*	0.80 [0.72, 0.90]	0.036	−0.03*	0.81 [0.71, 0.91]	0.036
Mathematics achievement	−0.13***	0.40 [0.35, 0.46]	0.000	−0.13***	0.40 [0.35, 0.47]	0.000
Disruptive behaviour	0.00	1.00 [0.96, 1.05]	0.948	0.00	1.00 [0.95, 1.06]	0.907
Class level						
Mathematics achievement	−0.06*	0.64 [0.47, 0.89]	0.013	−0.06*	0.64 [0.46, 0.91]	0.012
SES	−0.02	0.87 [0.56, 1.34]	0.452	−0.02	0.87 [0.53, 1.42]	0.449
Migration background	−0.03	0.78 [0.37, 1.66]	0.588	−0.04	0.78 [0.34, 1.81]	0.535
Disruptive behaviour				0.00	1.01 [0.90, 1.12]	0.686

Note: $R^2_{\text{Model 2.1}}=0.10$, $R^2_{\text{Model 2.2}}=0.10$, $R^2_{\text{Model 2.3}}=0.10$, $R^2_{\text{Model 2.4}}=0.10$.

Abbreviations: AME, average marginal effect; CI, 95% confidence interval; p, significance; OR, odds ratio.

* $p < 0.05$. ** $p < 0.01$. *** $p < 0.001$.

(Kvande et al., 2019). One possibility is that gender-based biases or stereotypes influence how support is allocated (Daniel & Wang, 2023; Petsko et al., 2022). This situation can be viewed from two perspectives: girls may not receive additional support despite having the same low mathematics achievement as boys, whereas boys may be identified as needing SE support even without demonstrating low achievement in mathematics. For students with a low SES background, it is not clear if SE support compensates for a lack of family resources, thus promoting greater equity, or if being labelled as needing SE support lowers teacher expectations of these students and possibly exacerbates existing inequalities. For these reasons, it remains ambiguous whether receiving SE support constitutes an advantage or a disadvantage for specific student groups, such as boys or students from low-SES backgrounds.

Limited role of a migration background

In contrast to the findings of previous studies, our analysis did not identify migration background as a significant predictor for receiving SE support. One possible explanation for this may be that migration background in our sample is strongly intertwined with other structural disadvantages that are themselves related to support allocation. Students with migration backgrounds are disproportionately represented in low-ability classes, which also show slightly higher rates of SE support (see Table 4). This pattern reflects earlier research showing that these students are more likely to be assigned to low-ability tracks when moving to secondary school (Felouzis & Charmillot, 2023), largely through correlated social and educational inequalities (Lüdemann & Schwerdt, 2013). Accordingly, the bivariate associations

TABLE 7 Logistic regression models: Prediction of the likelihood of receiving SE support based on school type.

Predictor	Model 3		
	AME%	OR [CI]	<i>p</i>
Individual level			
Gender	-0.12***	0.43 [0.34, 0.54]	0.000
Migration background	0.03	1.25 [0.98, 1.60]	0.332
SES	-0.03*	0.81 [0.71, 0.91]	0.037
Mathematics achievement	-0.13***	0.40 [0.35, 0.47]	0.000
Disruptive behaviour	0.00	1.00 [0.95, 1.06]	0.902
Class level			
Mathematics achievement	-0.06 [†]	0.69 [0.46, 1.01]	0.070
SES	-0.02	0.90 [0.56, 1.46]	0.534
Migration background	-0.04	0.77 [0.33, 1.79]	0.509
Disruptive behaviour	0.00	1.01 [0.90, 1.13]	0.650
School type	0.01	1.14 [0.75, 1.72]	0.415

Note: $R^2_{\text{Model 3}} = 0.10$.

Abbreviations: AME, average marginal effect; CI, 95% confidence interval; OR, odds ratio; *p*, significance.

[†]*p* < 0.10.

p* < 0.05. **p* < 0.001.

in our data (higher proportion of students with migration background among those who receive support, a significant but weak negative correlation with SES; see Tables 1 and 3) may reflect indirect pathways rather than a direct ‘migration effect’. In other words, once SES and achievement are considered, the remaining unique contribution of migration background can become small or statistically unstable. This interpretation aligns with reviews arguing that migration-related disparities in special education are often explained by the intersection of migration background with socioeconomic resources and achievement rather than migration background alone (Blossfeld & Nester, 2024; Dumont et al., 2014).

In addition, context-dependent identification processes may further weaken any independent effect of migration background. The descriptive statistics indicate that students with a migration background are relatively strongly represented in our sample, which means many classes include comparatively high proportions of students with migration backgrounds. Limited between-class variation in the proportion of students with a migration background may have reduced the statistical power for detecting any independent effect of migration background. In addition, difficulties related to language or learning may be more common in these classes, making the support needs of individual students less likely to be noticed. Consistent with research on peer-comparison and frog-pond effects (Hibel et al., 2010), this may reduce the likelihood that students with migration backgrounds are allocated to SE support.

Finally, the operationalization of migration background may also be important. In this study, migration background is captured as a dichotomous indicator based on the student and their parents' place of birth (born in Switzerland versus not), which necessarily collapses a great deal of heterogeneity. We did not analyse countries of origin or migration histories, although previous research suggests that these dimensions can be relevant for educational trajectories and support allocation (Müller & Stanat, 2006). As a result, potentially meaningful differences within the group of students with a migration background may be masked, which could further contribute to the absence of a detectable independent effect in the models.

The role of behavioural difficulties

Our analysis did not reveal a significant relationship between behavioural difficulties—as operationalized by disruptive behaviour—and receiving SE support. This contrasts with previous studies, which found that students with behavioural difficulties are more likely to receive support (Schwab et al., 2019), but aligns with Koßmann et al. (2024), who also found no individual-level effect. The inconsistency may be due to different operationalizations of behavioural difficulties across studies. In this study behaviour was assessed using teacher ratings, which introduces the possibility of perception bias. Previous research has shown that teachers may evaluate student behaviour differently depending on their socioeconomic background (Glock & Kleen, 2022). This suggests that the measurement of behavioural difficulties may partially reflect teacher perceptions rather than objective differences in student behaviour. However, our data showed no correlation between SES and disruptive behaviour (see Table 1). Beyond measurement issues, the absence of an association between disruptive behaviour and SE support may also be a reflection of the selection processes in the support system. This study focused on low-threshold SE support. Students with more severe behavioural difficulties could have been allocated to more intensive support measures or special education settings beyond the scope of our study. As a result, the remaining variation in disruptive behaviour within our sample may not be strongly related to the allocation of this type of support. Therefore, this selection effect could explain the lack of a significant association. Our findings raise the broader question of whether behavioural difficulties are sufficiently acknowledged as requiring additional support in the Swiss context and whether current practices adequately address them. The absence of a clear link between behavioural difficulties, as measured via disruptive behaviour, and the allocation of SE support raises the question about whether students with such needs are being adequately identified and supported (Norwich, 2014). One possible explanation is that behavioural problems

may be interpreted more as disciplinary or classroom management issues than as indicators of special educational needs. However, if behavioural challenges are not recognized as requiring SE support, there is a risk that affected students may not receive the assistance necessary to meet their needs, which could negatively impact their educational trajectories.

Impact of class composition characteristics

Individual characteristics such as mathematics achievement, SES and gender were significant predictors of receiving SE support when accounting for the class mean achievement level. In addition, a low mean class achievement increased the likelihood of receiving SE support. Other compositional characteristics—the proportion of students with a migration background, mean SES or mean disruptive behaviour—had no significant effect and did not alter the effect or significance of individual-level predictors. This suggests that support allocation is mostly shaped by individual characteristics and the mathematics achievement level of the class rather than by class composition as a whole. Our findings indicate that class mean mathematics achievement level is the most significant compositional characteristic, although the direction of the effect observed in our analysis differs from previous research (Kölm et al., 2020; Koßmann et al., 2024); the lower the class mean mathematics achievement, the more likely students are to receive SE support. The discrepancy may be due to differences in sample composition. Unlike the primary school populations of those previous studies, our sample includes only secondary school students in low- and mixed-ability classes. There are no high-ability classes in the sample. Furthermore, tracking and different school types may also help explain these findings. This issue will be addressed in the next section.

Relevance of the school type

When school type is included in the analysis, the effect of class mean achievement remains but is only significant at the 10% level, suggesting that structural selection has already taken place through class grouping policy. Differences in class achievement are thus likely to reflect the way students were allocated to secondary schools (Dumont et al., 2013; Felouzis & Charmillot, 2023). At the individual level, factors such as achievement, gender and SES remain predictive for receiving SE support. While school type itself was not a significant predictor, descriptive results show a higher proportion of students receiving SE support in low-ability tracks. This points to two related dynamics: first, consistent with prior findings (Ruijs, 2017), students being defined

as having special educational needs are often placed in low-ability tracks. Second, SE support is more available in these tracks, possibly reflecting both the higher concentration of students with identified needs and the allocation of additional resources. This finding is somewhat unexpected, given that tracking is explicitly designed to account for differences in students' learning needs and achievement levels. This highlights the role of institutional structures in shaping access to support and underscores the need to examine how school type in secondary education enables or limits inclusive education.

Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings of this study. First, the effect of academic achievement was investigated by only analysing mathematics achievement. Previous research has shown that mathematical competency correlates with language competency (Artelt et al., 2001). When different domains of achievement are considered simultaneously, mathematics achievement emerges as the stronger predictor for identifying special educational needs than reading achievement (Kölm et al., 2020; Koßmann et al., 2024). Therefore, mathematics achievement can be used as a valid indicator of overall academic achievement. However, the findings may not be fully generalizable and including other measures of academic achievement could improve our understanding of the factors influencing the allocation of SE support. Other factors, such as cross-curricular competencies or social-emotional factors, may also influence the decision to provide SE support. Second, the study is not representative of the entire secondary school population because it excludes students from high-ability classes and classes without access to low-threshold support measures. This limits the generalizability of the findings, particularly to educational settings with academically advanced students. In a representative sample including high-ability tracks, migration background might have emerged as a stronger predictor for receiving SE support, given the prior evidence that students with a migration background are underrepresented in high-ability classes due to ability tracking. Third, it should be noted that the present study examines the effects of selected characteristics while controlling the other variables. For example, it does not explore to what extent boys with a low SES are more likely to be assigned to SE support than boys with a high SES. Fourth, the measurement of SES with student self-assessment on a family wealth scale has limitations because key factors such as parental education or occupational status are not captured by the WEALTH scale (OECD, 2018b). These indicators could not be collected because of the conditions of the larger project.

CONCLUSIONS

This study provides valuable insights into individual and class-level characteristics associated with the allocation of SE support at the secondary level. The results show that boys and students from lower-SES backgrounds are more likely to receive SE support, even when mathematics achievement is controlled for. This suggests that support allocation may be related to a wide range of student needs, and the higher probability of SE support among students with a lower SES cannot simply be explained by lower mathematics achievement. In addition, class compositional characteristics matter: students in classes with a lower mean achievement level had a higher probability of receiving SE support than students in classes with a higher mean achievement level. This indicates that support allocation is shaped not only by individual needs but also by broader structural and compositional factors.

In secondary education, where students are often tracked based on achievement, these dynamics may be particularly relevant. Tracking and SE support are both intended to address differences in student achievement, yet they also carry the risk of reproducing social inequality. Our findings indicate that boys and students from socially less privileged families might be doubly affected: they are overrepresented in low-ability tracks and more frequently identified as requiring SE support.

Low-threshold measures are meant to support learning and behavioural difficulties without necessitating a formal diagnosis. Our analysis did not show a significant association between disruptive behaviour and SE support. This raises questions about whether the system adequately identifies behavioural needs that may require support.

While receiving SE support can, in principle, benefit students, it is important to consider how this support is implemented. The effectiveness of SE support depends largely on whether students receive targeted high-quality assistance from well-qualified special education teachers and whether this support is provided without lowering academic expectations or narrowing the curriculum (Kvande et al., 2019). Merely identifying students as needing SE support without providing targeted assistance may lead to unintended consequences, such as lower expectations or stigmatization. Therefore, further research is needed to examine both the long-term effects and effectiveness of SE support, particularly how it is perceived and its potential impact on students' educational trajectories, and the role of structural and institutional factors in shaping the allocation to SE support and its consequences for students.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Eva-Maria Holzer: Conceptualization; methodology; formal analysis; data curation; investigation; project

administration; validation; writing – original draft; writing – review and editing. **Maria Wehren-Müller:** Methodology; data curation; investigation. **Mireille Tabin:** Data curation; writing – review and editing; investigation. **Janina Kraft:** Data curation; investigation. **Elisabeth Moser Opitz:** Project administration; writing – review and editing; supervision; funding acquisition.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have no known conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings will be available on SwissUbase <https://doi.org/10.48573/f8h6-ae55>.

ETHICS STATEMENT

The study was approved by the ethics committee of the Faculty of Art and Social Sciences of the University of Zurich.

CONSENT

Participation was voluntary. Written informed consent was obtained from both students and parents after they had been provided with detailed information about the study.

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Endnotes

ⁱ Low SES generally refers to families with limited financial resources, lower levels of parental education and/or unstable employment. Although students from families with low SES in Switzerland may be eligible for general social benefits or financial support, these forms of assistance are not part of school-based provision; they are provided by other social welfare institutions.

ⁱⁱ In Switzerland, special education teachers are required to hold a master's degree in special needs education in addition to a teaching qualification for primary or secondary education (Kronenberg, 2021).

ⁱⁱⁱ The scale is provided in [Appendix 1](#).

^{iv} None of the participating students selected the *diverse* gender option.

^vThe scale is provided in [Appendix 2](#).

^{vi}Information on the language students spoke at home by was also collected. We considered using first language instead of migration background in the models. However, the two variables were highly correlated, resulting in multicollinearity when entered simultaneously. Model results were substantively identical when using first language instead of migration background. For reasons of comparability with prior research, migration background was retained in the final models.

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APPENDIX 1

Disruptive Behaviour Scale

Instrument and coding

Source	Eckstein et al. (2018) with minor adaptations of wording and scaling to suit the target grade level of the present study.
Instruction	In the past 2 weeks, how often has [name of student] done these things in your classroom? Please go through the statements one by one and indicate how often the student has shown each behaviour.
Response	Single choice
Format	7-point frequency scale

Instrument and coding

Coding	Never: 1
	1 time: 2
	2 times: 3
	3 times: 4
	4 times: 5
	5 times: 6
	More than 5 times: 7

Dimension	Item	Wording
Disruptive behaviour	1_id ^a	Did not properly participate in math class but instead did something else.
	2_id	Spoke out in math class without raising their hand, even though they were supposed to.
	3_id	Talked to others during math class, even though they were supposed to be quiet.
	4_id	Made noise in math class.
	5_id	Interrupted the math teacher.
	6_id	Did not follow the teacher's instructions right away.
	7_id	Gave cheeky answers to the math teacher.

^a id=identification number of student in question.

APPENDIX 2
WEALTH Scale

Instrument and coding

Source	OECD (2018b)
Instruction	How many of the following items do you have at home? Please enter one answer for each item.
Response	Single choice
Format	4-point count scale
Coding	None: 1 One: 2 Two: 3 Three or more: 4

Dimension	Item	Wording
WEALTH	1	Television
	2	Car
	3	Room with bath or shower
	4	Mobile phone with internet access
	5	Computer (PC, laptop or notebook)
	6	E-book reader (e.g., Amazon®Kindle™, Kobo, Sony)
	7	Musical instrument (e.g. guitar, piano, excluding recorder)
